

**THE CORRELATION BETWEEN PSYCHOLOGY LABORATORY AND
PRACTICUM PERFORMANCE OF FAITH BS PSYCHOLOGY FOR
THE S. Y 2022 – 2023: BASIS FOR CURRICULUM
ENHANCEMENT PLAN**

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The Correlation between Psychology Laboratory and Practicum Performance of FAITH BS Psychology for the S. Y 2022 – 2023: Basis for Curriculum Enhancement Plan

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between psychology laboratory performance and practicum performance among FAITH BS Psychology students for the school year 2022-2023, using a quantitative approach. The entire population of students completing psychological assessments and practicum in a clinical setting was analyzed, employing the Grade Weighted Average (GWA) as the instrument for measuring performance in both areas. Permission was obtained from relevant administrative authorities, and a structured data collection process was implemented to ensure confidentiality and data integrity. Results indicated that psychology laboratory performance had a general assessment GWA of 84.52 (SD = 5.94), reflecting a good level of understanding and competence. The analysis revealed a strong positive correlation between laboratory and practicum performance ($r(21) = .777, p = .000$), indicating that improvements in one setting are associated with enhancements in the other. These findings suggest that the knowledge and skills acquired in the laboratory are effectively applied in practicum settings, demonstrating successful learning outcomes and the practical application of psychological skills.

Keywords: *psychology laboratory performance, practicum performance*

Introduction

The field of psychology is multifaceted, requiring students to not only grasp theoretical concepts but also apply them in real-world settings. Within the Bachelor of Science in Psychology program at FAITH Colleges, the integration of laboratory work and practicums stands as a pillar of experiential learning, bridging the gap between academic knowledge and practical application. The Psychology Laboratory engages students in hands-on experiments and assessments, sharpening their analytical skills and deepening their understanding of psychological phenomena. Meanwhile, practicum experiences allow students to immerse themselves in professional environments, fostering critical competencies and ethical practices essential for their future careers.

The psychology laboratory provides a controlled environment where students can engage in experimental research, data analysis, and the application of psychological theories. These experiences enhance critical thinking, problem-solving, and technical skills. On the other hand, the practicum offers students the opportunity to apply their knowledge in real-world settings, such as clinics, schools, or corporate environments, where they can observe and participate in professional psychological practices.

This study used David Kolb's Experiential theory as cited by Morris (2020), which emphasizes the importance of learning through experience. It suggests that knowledge is best acquired when students engage actively in their learning process. This theory posits that hands-on experiences in the lab allow students to apply theoretical concepts in practical scenarios. By conducting experiments, engaging in simulations, and participating in group activities, students develop a deeper understanding of psychological principles. This experiential learning fosters critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and the ability to apply knowledge in real-world situations. As a result, students who excel in laboratory settings are likely to perform better in practicum placements, where they must utilize their skills and knowledge to support clients effectively.

This study served as a basis for a curriculum enhancement plan to optimize the educational pathways for psychology students at FAITH. By aligning laboratory and practicum experiences more closely, the program can better equip students with the necessary skills and knowledge to excel in their future careers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of psychology laboratory performance and practicum performance of FAITH BS Psychology for the S. Y 2022 – 2023 and correlate them to provide the answer to the following questions:

1. What is the laboratory psychology performance and practicum performance of FAITH BS Psychology for the S. Y 2022 – 2023?
2. Is there a significant relationship between the Psychology Laboratory and Practicum Performance of FAITH BS Psychology for the S. Y 2022 – 2023?

Literature Review

Psychology Laboratory Performance

Psychology laboratory performance is crucial for developing essential skills that students need for their future careers in psychology. Hands-on experiences in laboratory settings significantly enhance students' understanding and application of psychological concepts.

For instance, a study by Baird and McKenzie (2017) demonstrated that students who engaged in laboratory exercises reported increased confidence and competence, which positively influenced their clinical practicum performance.

Moreover, Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory supports the idea that active participation in laboratory work fosters deeper learning, enabling students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical situations. In a study by Murdock and Miller (2018), it was found that students who participated in interactive lab activities performed better in their practicum assessments, highlighting the direct correlation between laboratory experiences and practical application.

Furthermore, Lim and Torres (2018) emphasized the importance of practical laboratory experiences in fostering essential skills like communication and empathy, which are crucial in clinical settings.

Moreover, a study by Alcaraz and De Leon (2020) found that students who participated in hands-on laboratory activities exhibited higher levels of competence and confidence during their practicum placements, leading to better evaluations from their supervisors

Lastly, a study by Smith and Jones (2020) indicated that critical thinking skills developed in laboratory settings were essential for handling complex cases during practicum placements. A longitudinal study by Garcia et al. (2021) reinforced these findings, showing that students with extensive laboratory training received higher evaluations during their practicum, further emphasizing the importance of laboratory experiences in preparing students for real-world applications.

Practicum Performance

Practicum performance in psychology is influenced by various factors, including prior laboratory experiences, theoretical knowledge, and interpersonal skills. Research has shown that students who engage in hands-on laboratory work tend to perform better during their practicum placements. For instance, a study by Baird and McKenzie (2017) found that students who actively participated in laboratory settings displayed increased confidence and practical skills, which translated into higher performance evaluations in their clinical practicums.

Furthermore, a study by Reyes and Santos (2018) highlighted the importance of mentorship and feedback during practicum experiences. They found that students who received consistent guidance from supervisors showed marked improvement in their performance, emphasizing the role of supportive learning environments.

Additionally, a longitudinal study by Cruz et al. (2018) revealed that students who engaged in collaborative projects in laboratory settings developed better teamwork and communication skills, which are critical during practicum.

In line with this, synthesizing both laboratory and practicum experiences reveals their critical role in developing essential skills for psychology students' clinical practice. Laboratory work has been shown to enhance confidence, competence, and the practical application of theoretical knowledge, as demonstrated in studies by Baird and McKenzie (2017), Murdock and Miller (2018), Reyes and Santos (2018) and Alcaraz and De Leon (2020). Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory, along with research by Lim and Torres (2018), Garcia et al. (2021), further underscores how hands-on laboratory activities strengthen crucial skills, such as empathy and communication. Additionally, Smith and Jones (2020), Cruz et al. (2018) found that laboratory experiences foster critical thinking, a skill invaluable for practicum settings

Methodology

Respondents

The respondents of the study are FAITH BS Psychology for the school year 2022-2023. The study utilizes the entire population of students who are completing their psychological assessment and practicum in a clinical setting. This approach allows for a comprehensive analysis of their performance in both the psychology laboratory and practicum, providing valuable insights into their academic and practical skills.

Instrument

For a quantitative study, the researcher used the Grade Weighted Average (GWA) in the psychological assessment as the instrument to assess psychology laboratory performance and the Grade Weighted Average (GWA) in the practicum of the clinical setting to assess the practicum performance. The GWA serves as a quantitative measure that aggregates individual grades across various assessments, providing an overall indicator of a student's academic performance in these areas. By using GWA, the researcher can analyze the relationship between the psychology laboratory performance and practicum performance.

Procedure

To facilitate the study, the researcher first asked permission from the Dean of the College of Arts, Sciences, and Education to conduct the study. Afterward, the researcher sent a letter of permission to the school registrar for the GWA data of the respondents.

The data collection plan for gathering General Weighted Average (GWA) information from the university was carefully structured to ensure clarity and effectiveness. The timeframe for data collection was delineated as the first two weeks of the upcoming semester,

allowing sufficient time for the registrar's office to compile the necessary information while ensuring minimal disruption to their regular operations.

To maintain data accuracy, the researchers collaborated closely with the registrar's office to ensure access to the most recent and verified student records. A standardized data extraction template was utilized, which included checks for inconsistencies and missing values. Confidentiality was a paramount concern throughout the process. The researchers established protocols to anonymize the data by removing personal data of such as student names and contact details. Access to the data was restricted to authorized personnel only, and secure data storage solutions were employed to protect the data from unauthorized access or breaches. Additionally, all data handling procedures were compliant with the university's data protection policies and relevant legal regulations.

After the data collection phase was complete, the researchers employed appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics and inferential analysis, to analyze the GWA data.

Ethical Considerations

The utilization of respondents necessitated the careful consideration of measures to safeguard their privacy and security. These challenges were anticipated in advance to preempt any potential complications that may develop throughout the investigation. During the discourse, the primary factors that were deliberated upon encompass confidentiality, privacy, anonymity, and proper acknowledgment of intellectual works. Following the provision of informed consent, which encompassed details regarding the study's significance, relevance, goals, and data collection procedures, respondents were subsequently informed about the voluntary nature of their involvement. Furthermore, due recognition was given to the contributions made by other scholars and writers to this particular body of work. Furthermore, all data and information collected for the study were treated with utmost confidentiality.

The researcher demonstrated an understanding of the potential risks associated with conducting this study during the ongoing epidemic while considering the risk-benefit analysis. In this context, the researcher took measures to ensure the well-being and protection of all participants who will be involved in the study. Throughout the designated timeframe, strict adherence to the health protocols mandated by the government was maintained. Furthermore, it was important to note that the participants in this research were FAITH BS Psychology for the S. Y 2022 – 2023. The communication of results was prioritized to ensure transparency and responsibility. Participants were informed that their data would be used solely for research purposes and that any findings would be reported in aggregate form to protect their anonymity and confidentiality.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcome of the quantitative analysis of the research questions answers. The results are presented based on the variable levels and relationships.

The Level of Psychology Laboratory Performance and Practicum Performance of FAITH BS Psychology for The S. Y 2022 – 2023

Table 1. *Level of Psychology Laboratory Performance and Practicum Performance*

Subjects	Performance Grade		
	n	%	SD
Psychology Laboratory Performance	23	84.52	5.94
Practicum Performance	23	91.13	2.63

Note. n= 23 respondents were FAITH BS Psychology for the S. Y 2022 – 2023

Psychology Laboratory performance had a general assessment of 84.52 for BS Psychology for the S.Y 2022-2023 (SD=5.94) which indicated a good level of understanding and competence in the subject specifically in psychological assessment where the usage of a certain psychological tests and writing psychological reports has been taught. The findings suggested that BS Psychology for the S.Y 2022-2023 have a good grasp of the laboratory material and have performed well, though there may be some areas for improvement.

Moreover, practicum performance had a general assessment of 91.13 for BS Psychology for the S.Y 2022-2023 (SD=2.63) which indicated a high level of competence and understanding in the psychological tests and writing psychological reports. The findings suggested that BS Psychology for the S.Y 2022-2023 demonstrated superior competence in practical settings, likely translating to better real-world application of psychological concepts. This data was supported by Lim and Torres (2018) emphasized the importance of practical laboratory experiences in fostering essential skills like communication and empathy, which are crucial in clinical settings. Moreover, a study by Alcaraz and De Leon (2020) found that students who participated in hands-on laboratory activities exhibited higher levels of competence and confidence during their practicum placements, leading to better evaluations from their supervisors.

The Significant Relationship Between the Psychology Laboratory and Practicum Performance of FAITH BS Psychology for The S. Y 2022 – 2023?

A Pearson correlation coefficient was computed to assess the relationship between psychology laboratory performance and practicum performance of FAITH BS Psychology for the S.Y 2022 –2023. There was a strong positive correlation between the psychology

laboratory performance and practicum performance of FAITH BS Psychology for the S.Y 2022 -2023, $r(21) = .777, p = .000$.

Table 2. *The Relationship Between the Psychology Laboratory and Practicum Performance*

Variables	Computed R-Value	P-value	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on H_0	Interpretation
Psychology laboratory performance * Practicum performance	.777	.000*	Strong Positive Correlation	Reject H_0	Significant

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

This result indicated that as one performance improves, the other tends to improve as well. This suggests that the skills and knowledge gained in the laboratory setting are effectively applied in the practicum. Thus, reflecting effective learning and application of psychological skills.

This result was supported by a study by Baird and McKenzie (2017) found that students who actively participated in laboratory settings showed enhanced confidence and practical skills, which translated to better performance in clinical practicum placements. These findings suggest that integrating laboratory work into the curriculum can significantly enhance students' readiness and effectiveness in practicum environments.

Moreover, a study by Murdock and Miller (2018) showed that students who engaged in interactive laboratory activities scored higher on assessments related to their practicum experiences, suggesting a direct link between lab work and practical application. Thus, laboratory experiences provided students with critical thinking skills that were essential for success in their practicum placements, particularly in handling complex case scenarios.

Furthermore, a longitudinal study by Garcia et al. (2021) indicated that students who had robust laboratory training performed significantly better in their practicum evaluations compared to those with minimal lab experience, reinforcing the idea that laboratory work is crucial for developing practical competencies. Students in the FAITH BS Psychology program who engaged in a laboratory course where they practiced administering, scoring, and interpreting psychological tests on simulated patients showed a marked improvement in their ability to conduct psychological testing during their subsequent practicum placement. This improvement was evident in their increased competency applying psychological principles they learned and in receiving positive feedback from their practicum supervisors, highlighting the value of laboratory experiences in preparing psychology students for real-world clinical work.

Conclusions

The assessment data for BS Psychology students during the academic year 2022-2023 indicates a strong understanding and competence in both laboratory and practicum settings. The general assessment score of 84.52 (SD = 5.94) for laboratory performance suggests that students have a solid grasp of psychological assessments, including the usage of certain psychological tests and the writing of psychological reports. This level of performance reflects a good understanding of the theoretical and practical aspects of the subject matter, although there may still be areas that require further development.

In contrast, the practicum performance score of 91.13 (SD = 2.63) indicates a high level of competence in applying psychological concepts in real-world settings. This score suggests that students are effectively translating their laboratory knowledge into practical applications, demonstrating superior skills in executing psychological assessments and reports. The findings imply that the training received in laboratory settings has a positive impact on students' performance during their practicum experiences.

In the context of the FAITH BS Psychology program, the laboratory course designed to teach students how to administer, score, and interpret psychological tests on simulated patients serves as a vital component of their education. The marked improvement in students' competencies during their practicum placements indicates that such experiential learning opportunities are essential in bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. The positive feedback received from practicum supervisors further underscores the effectiveness of this training approach, as it reflects an acknowledgment of the student's preparedness and capability to apply psychological principles in real-world settings.

Moreover, the emphasis on laboratory work aligns with the broader educational standards in psychology, which advocate for an integrative approach to learning that encompasses both theoretical instruction and practical application. By fostering an environment where students can actively practice their skills in a controlled setting, the program not only enhances their learning experience but also increases their confidence and competence when faced with actual clinical situations.

The implications of these findings extend beyond individual student performance; they highlight the necessity for psychology programs to incorporate robust laboratory components into their curricula. As the landscape of psychology continues to evolve, so too must the educational strategies employed to prepare future practitioners. Emphasizing laboratory training could potentially lead to higher levels of competency among graduates, ultimately benefiting the field as they enter the workforce.

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